

transmission exceeded 75% in some experiments.

Results of experiments to evaluate heat therapy's ability to eradicate the pathogen from infected seed are presented in the table. Moderate dry heat therapy substantially reduced pathogen recovery from seed, but 65°C for 6 d was required to completely eradicate it. No deleterious effect on germination was detected by even higher heat treatment (70°C, 6 d).

Although this is the first report of sheath rot and grain discoloration caused by *Pseudomonas* spp. in Latin America, BSBR has probably been in the region for some time. BSBR has been reported in Japan and in high-altitude rice in Burundi, East Africa. A disease with identical symptomatology, but attributed to an unidentified bacterium, has been reported in southern Brazil (bacterial brown stripe). Reports of dirty panicle, glume discoloration, and manchado de grano have been increasing around the world.

The striking similarity between the sheath symptoms described and those attributed to *Sarocladium oryzae* (sheath rot), combined with the

Effect of heat treatment on recovery of *P. fuscovaginae* from spotted seed of 2 varieties.^a CIAT, Cali, Colombia.

Temperature (°C)	Recovery of <i>P. fuscovaginae</i>					
	1 d		3 d		6 d	
	Infected seed (no.)	Total seed (no.)	Infected seed (no.)	Total seed (no.)	Infected seed (no.)	Total seed (no.)
	<i>CICA8</i>					
55	107	396	235	418	24	333
60	153	591	56	443	9	350
65	22	584	2	227	0	401
Control (untreated seed)	233	339	235	396	280	431
	<i>Oryzica 1</i>					
55	102	421	105	338	12	374
60	47	377	38	369	5	234
65	18	375	12	375	0	403
Control (untreated seed)	318	400	115	327	115	383

^aInfection identified by pathogenic fluorescent bacteria on King's B medium.

difficulty researchers often encounter reisolating *S. oryzae* from the grain, suggest that symptoms attributed to the fungus in some cases may be caused by *P. fuscovaginae*. In Colombia, symptomatology and the association of this bacterium with dirty panicle suggest that it is among the primary causal agents.

CIAT has detected the pathogen in seed received in routine international germplasm exchanges from Asia and Africa. At CIAT, all seed received from and seed sent to national and international programs is treated with dry heat at 65°C and monitored to ensure that it is free of the bacterium. *S*

In vitro response of maize and rice isolates of *Rhizoctonia solani* to antibiotics and fungitoxicants

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We tested the effect of two antibiotics and five fungitoxicants on *Rhizoctonia solani* f. sp. *sasakii* using the food-poison technique and maize (R₁) and rice (R₆) isolates. Radial growth was measured at 24-h intervals.

Carbendazim, benodanil, and thiabendazole at 25-30 µg ai/ml completely inhibited growth of both isolates and showed fungistatic effects (see table). Both isolates were less sensitive to thiophanate-M, dichloroline, and aureofungin. Isolate

Fungitoxicant and antibiotic effect on radial growth of 2 *R. solani* isolates in vitro.^a

Fungitoxicant, antibiotic	Concentration (µg/ml)	Growth reduction (%)	
		Maize isolate	Rice isolate
Validamycin A	30.0	24.0	22.0
	36.0	24.5	24.5
	45.0	27.0	22.0
Aureofungin	3.0	39.5	56.0
	6.0	41.0	45.3
Benodanil	25.0	100.0	100.0
	37.5	100.0	100.0
	50.0	100.0	100.0
Carbendazim	25.0	100.0	100.0
	31.5	100.0	100.0
	50.0	100.0	100.0
Dichloroline	30.0	30.0	42.0
	60.0	30.0	39.0
	120.0	33.0	39.0
Thiabendazole	30.0	100.0	100.0
	45.0	100.0	100.0
	60.0	100.0	100.0
Thiophanate-methyl	35.0	100.0	45.0
	56.5	100.0	32.0
	70.0	100.0	30.0

^aAv of 3 replications.

R₁ was more sensitive to thiophanate-M than was isolate R₆.

A special effect was observed with validamycin-A (30% EC, Takeda Chemical Industries Ltd., Japan). Radial growth of *R. solani* was restricted, resulting in the formation of an atypical colony.

In an additional test, benodanil, carbendazim (5, 10, 15, 20 µg ai/ml), and thiobendazole (3, 6, 9, 12, µg ai/ml) inhibited growth of 4 maize isolates (R₁-R₄) and 2 rice isolates (R₅-R₆). ♂

Serological identification of tungro viruses in isolates from 4 states of India

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We collected tungro isolates from Coimbatore and Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu; Cuttack and Simliguda, Orissa; Patna and Pusa, Bihar; and Barrackpore, Burdwan, Malda, and Hooghly, West Bengal, and inoculated them into 15-d-old Jaya seedlings. For serological identification, different isolates preserved under insect-proof conditions were inoculated to 20-d-old Taichung Native 1 (TNI) seedlings at 5 leathoppers/plant. One week after inoculation, the second leaf of each seedling was crushed in a pestle and mortar with 1 ml of Tris buffer (0.05 M)/10 mg leaf tissue. After homogenation, the sap was refrigerated 1/2 h to settle host particles. The supernatant sap (50 µl) mixed with an equal amount of latex suspension sensitized with antisera to RTBV or RTSV was rigorously shaken for about 1 h.

One drop of this suspension was observed under a microscope (100 ×) and scored based on clumping of latex particles.

A positive reaction for both RTSV and RTBV was found in all isolates, indicating that these two viruses are involved in causing tungro epidemics in India. ♂

Horizontal and vertical spread of rice sheath blight (ShB)

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Horizontal and vertical development of ShB has been documented, but little is known about disease spread from a single inoculated spot in a field. Highly susceptible Lebonnet was drill-planted in 2.3- × 3.7-m plots with 4 replications. At 20 cm between rows, plant population was 3,500,000/ha.

One plant per plot was inoculated at floodwater level with 1-10 pregerminated (in water agar for 12 h) sclerotia. Horizontal and vertical ShB progression were recorded in centimeters and number of infected leaf sheaths at

5-d intervals starting 7 d after inoculation. Five plants within and next to the hill with the inoculated plant were used to measure vertical ShB development.

All sclerotia initiated infection on the inoculated plant. Horizontal and vertical ShB spread increased from 7 to 22 d after inoculation (DI) (Table 1, 2). The spread was faster from row to row than within row. But the increase was larger within row. At 22 DI, horizontal ShB development reached 93.3 cm within row for some treatments and 90.0 cm between rows.

Inoculum number had no significant effect on spread. All treatments were similar in causing and spreading ShB. It is not clear why the spread from row to row was faster than within row. ♂

Table 1. Horizontal spread of ShB within row.^a

Sclerotia (no./plant)	Distance ^b (cm) from point of inoculation			
	7 DI	12 DI	17 DI	22 DI
0	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
1	0 a	3.2 ab	8.5 ab	22.0 a
2	0.5 a	2.2 a	9.2 ab	37.2 abc
3	0 a	4.5 ab	11.2 abc	18.5 a
4	0.5 a	3.7 ab	14.7 abcd	27.3 ab
5	0 a	1.5 b	6.3 ab	14.5 a
6	0 a	15.3 b	33.8 cd	86.0 bc
7	0.5 a	5.2 ab	19.5 abcd	41.0 abc
8	0.5 a	7.7 ab	23.7 abcd	48.8 abc
9	0.5 a	7.3 ab	29.3 bcd	82.5 bc
10	0.8 a	15.5 b	37.2 d	93.3 c
CV	47.1	25.3	20.3	20.5

^aMeans with the same letter are not significantly different by the Duncan-Waller multiple range test. DI = days after inoculation. ^b3-yr means (1980-82).

Table 2. Horizontal (H, between rows) and vertical (V) spread of ShB.^a

Sclerotia (no./plant)	Distance ^b (cm) from point of inoculation							
	7 DI		12 DI		17 DI		22 DI	
	H	V	H	V	H	V	H	V
0	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
1	6.7 b	0.3 b	16.7 b	1.3 b	23.3 a	2.2 bc	26.7 b	3.2 b
2	20.0 c	1.0 bcd	23.3 b	1.5 bc	33.3 ab	2.7 bc	50.7 c	3.5 b
3	13.3 bc	0.7 ab	23.3 b	2.0 bc	30.0 ab	3.2 c	43.3 bc	3.5 b
4	16.7 c	0.8 bc	26.7 bc	1.8 bc	33.3 ab	2.7 bc	50.0 bc	3.5 b
5	13.3 bc	0.7 ab	23.3 b	1.5 bc	40.0 abc	2.0 b	50.0 bc	2.8 b
6	20.0 c	0.7 ab	36.7 cd	1.7 bc	63.3 d	2.5 bc	90.0 d	3.0 b
7	16.7 c	0.8 bc	23.3 b	2.0 bc	46.7 abcd	3.0 c	66.0 cd	4.0 b
8	20.0 c	1.0 bcd	40.0 d	1.7 bc	38.3 ab	3.8 bc	70.0 cd	4.0 b
9	20.0 c	1.3 d	36.7 cd	2.0 bc	53.3 bcd	3.0 c	63.3 cd	3.7 b
10	20.0 c	1.2 cd	40.0 d	3.2 c	60.0 cd	3.2 c	55.7 c	3.5 b
CV	34.6	40.3	34.2	36.7	45.6	29.7	42.6	30.0

^aMeans with the same letter are not significantly different by the Duncan-Waller multiple range test. ^b3-yr means (1980-82).